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Resveratrol and COVID-19

Domina Petric, MD

I hypothesized in March 2020 that resveratrol (from grape seeds and red wine) is an interesting molecule for further research on SARS-CoV-2 because it has been found that it has some in vitro anti-viral effect on coronaviruses. Based on the available up to date published research resveratrol can be used alone or in combination with trace elements (copper, zinc) in prophylaxis and/or treatment of COVID-19, but more clinical investigation is necessary to determine the exact clinical efficacy and precise dose regimen.

INTRODUCTION

I hypothesized in March 2020 that resveratrol (from grape seeds and red wine) is an interesting molecule for further research on SARS-CoV-2 because it has been found that it has some *in vitro* anti-viral effect on coronaviruses¹.

AN UPDATE

In a study (Yang and coworkers) researchers observed that resveratrol exhibits capacity to inhibit SARS-CoV-2 infection in the in-vitro cell culture, and concluded that these results suggest a potential utility of resveratrol as a novel therapy for COVID-19 infection².

Ramdani and Bachari published a report that aims to highlight resveratrol as possible therapeutic candidate in SARS-CoV-2 infection. The antiviral efficacy of

resveratrol was demonstrated for several viruses, including coronavirus. Resveratrol was shown to mitigate the major pathways involved in the pathogenesis of SARS-CoV-2, including regulation of the renin-angiotensin system (RAS) and expression of angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2), stimulation of immune system and downregulation of pro-inflammatory cytokines release. It was also reported to promote SIRT1 and p53 signaling pathways and increase cytotoxic T lymphocytes (CTLs) and natural killer (NK) immune cells. Resveratrol was demonstrated to be a stimulator of fetal hemoglobin and a potent antioxidant, by trapping reactive oxygen species (ROS). According to these reports, authors concluded that resveratrol could be proposed as potential therapeutic in the treatment of SARS-CoV-2³.

Mark Marinella concluded in his article that although randomized trial data are not yet available for indomethacin and resveratrol for treatment of or slowing progression of SARS-CoV-2 infection, these agents should be considered by the medical community as potentially worthy of further study as therapeutic adjuncts, given the relative safety, accessibility and low cost⁴.

In an ongoing clinical trial (NCT04542993) investigators will test the hypothesis that in ambulatory, non-hospitalized patients with SARS-CoV-2 infection is possible to utilize resveratrol as a transporter for zinc treatment as means to minimize viral load and severity of resulting COVID-19 disease⁵.

Giovinazzo and coworkers concluded in their review that bioactive phytochemicals, such as polyphenols (resveratrol) may become promising tools for the treatment of COVID-19 in reducing the hyper-activation of cytokines such as TNF α , IL-1 β , IL-6, and IL-8. Such nutrients with anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties may prevent or attenuate the inflammatory and vascular manifestations associated with COVID-19. Plant bioactive molecules can be produced by renewable and low-cost source and this plays an important value for the enhancement and

the exploitation of by-products of food chains. Moreover, following healthy dietary patterns may have beneficial effects to contrast infection⁶.

Mitra and coworkers conducted a study comprised of 230 patients with severe COVID-19 requiring inhaled oxygen who were admitted in a single tertiary care hospital in Mumbai between April 1 and May 13 2020. Thirty of these patients received, in addition to standard care, **resveratrol** and **copper** at doses of 5.6 mg and 560 ng, respectively, orally, once every 6 hours, until discharge or death. These doses were based on their pre-clinical studies, and were nearly 50 times and 2000 times less, respectively, than those recommended as health supplements. A multivariable-adjusted analysis was used to model the outcome of death in these patients and evaluate factors associated with this event. A binary logistic regression analysis was used, with age, sex, presence of comorbidities and receipt of resveratrol-copper as covariates. Data were updated as of May 30 2020. The number of deaths in resveratrol-copper and standard care only groups were 7/30 (23.3%, 95% CI 8.1%-38.4%) and 89/200 (44.5%, 95% CI 37.6%-51.3%), respectively. In multivariable analysis, age >50 years [odds ratio (OR) 2.558, 95% CI 1.454-4.302, $P=0.0011$] and female sex

(OR 1.939, 95% CI 1.079-3.482, $P=0.0267$) were significantly associated, while presence of comorbidities was not significantly associated (OR 0.713, 95% CI 0.405-1.256, $P=0.2421$) with death. There was a trend towards reduction in death in patients receiving resveratrol-copper (OR 0.413, 95% CI 0.164-1.039, $P=0.0604$)⁷.

CONCLUSION

Resveratrol is a bioactive polyphenol that mitigates the major pathways involved in the pathogenesis of SARS-CoV-2, including regulation of the renin-angiotensin system and expression of angiotensin-converting enzyme 2; stimulates immune system and downregulates pro-inflammatory cytokines release; promotes SIRT1 and p53 signaling pathways; and increases cytotoxic T lymphocytes and natural killer immune cells. Resveratrol was demonstrated to be a stimulator of fetal hemoglobin and a potent antioxidant, by trapping reactive oxygen species. It can also reduce the hyperactivation of cytokines such as TNF α , IL-1 β , IL-6, and IL-8.

Based on the available up to date published research resveratrol can be used alone or in combination with trace elements (copper,

zinc) in prophylaxis and/or treatment of COVID-19, but more clinical investigation is necessary to determine the exact clinical efficacy and precise dose regimen.

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